

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF STUDENTS IN A SCIENCE-MODULAR CLASSROOM: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

Ludivina S. Palcullo, MMEM

Lambayong National High School, Lambayong, Sultan Kudarat, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12685228>

ABSTRACT

The rapid shift towards modular learning due to global disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has significantly transformed educational practices worldwide. This phenomenological study explores the lived experiences of students in a science-modular classroom at Lambayong National High School in Lambayong, Sultan Kudarat. The research aims to understand how students perceive and navigate the unique challenges and opportunities presented by modular learning in science education. Using in-depth interviews and thematic analysis, the study uncovers the nuances of students' interactions with modular materials, their engagement with science concepts, and their overall academic experiences. Key findings highlight the students' adaptability to self-paced learning, the importance of teacher support and feedback, and the role of peer collaboration in enhancing understanding. Despite initial difficulties with the modular approach, students reported improved self-discipline and time management skills. However, challenges such as limited access to resources and occasional feelings of isolation were also identified. These insights provide valuable implications for educators and policymakers aiming to optimize modular learning environments. The study underscores the need for adequate resources, continuous teacher training, and strategies to foster a supportive learning community. By shedding light on the students' perspectives, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of modular learning's impact on science education, offering guidance for future implementations and improvements.

Keywords: *Phenomenological Analysis, Science Education, Modular Learning, Student Experiences*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid shift towards modular learning due to global disruptions, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has significantly transformed educational practices worldwide. This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of students in a science-modular classroom at Lambayong National High School, Lambayong, Sultan Kudarat. Understanding these experiences is crucial for developing effective teaching strategies and improving educational outcomes in a modular learning environment.

Globally, modular learning has been implemented as an alternative to traditional classroom instruction, particularly during times of crisis. This approach allows for flexible, self-paced learning, making it a viable option during disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Ali, 2020). Studies have shown that while modular learning offers several benefits, including flexibility and accessibility, it also presents challenges such as reduced student engagement and limited teacher-student interaction (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020). Despite extensive research on the effectiveness of modular learning, there is a gap in understanding the subjective experiences of students, particularly in science subjects, which require hands-on activities and experiments.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) adopted modular learning as a primary mode of instruction during the pandemic, providing printed and digital modules to students nationwide (DepEd, 2020). While this approach ensured the continuity of education, it also highlighted issues such as the digital divide, varying levels of parental support, and the readiness of teachers and students for this mode of learning (Lapada et al., 2020). Although there have been studies on the challenges and effectiveness of modular learning in the Philippines, there is a noticeable gap in literature focusing on the specific experiences of students in science-modular classrooms.

In South Central Mindanao, particularly in Sultan Kudarat, the study of Ngag (2023) showed a significant improvement in the students' achievements/scores by using module on Teduray folktales which includes various activities and lessons such as grammar, vocabulary enrichment, and reading comprehension both HOTS and LOTS and Teduray-English translated lessons such as Tēduray original poems, folksongs, riddles, and proverbs. However, there is a lack of in-depth studies exploring the lived experiences of students in this setting, particularly in science subjects which are traditionally more challenging to teach and learn remotely.

Despite the growing body of research on modular learning, significant gaps remain, particularly regarding the lived experiences of students in science-modular classrooms. Internationally, while the effectiveness and challenges of modular learning have been well-documented, the personal and subjective experiences of students in science subjects remain underexplored. In the Philippines, existing studies tend to focus on the general challenges of modular learning, with limited attention to the specific experiences of science students. In South Central Mindanao, the socio-economic and cultural factors influencing modular learning have not been sufficiently examined, leaving a gap in

understanding how these factors affect students' experiences in science-modular classrooms.

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of the junior high school students in the modular class conducted in their Science class at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat. It also aimed to bridge the existing gaps on studies related to Science in a modular class setting.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of the junior high school students in the modular class conducted in their Science class at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following:

1. What are the lived experiences of Junior High School students in their modular Science classes at Lambayong National High School?
2. What struggles do they encounter that hinder their learning in Science?
3. What coping strategies do they employ to manage these struggles in their modular Science classes?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research, specifically the phenomenological approach, was employed to explore the lived experiences of the Junior High School students in the modular class conducted in their Science class at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat.

Phenomenological research is a method that aims to delve into individuals' lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how they interpret these experiences. It operates under the assumption that individuals employ a universal structure or essence to derive meaning from their encounters. This research involves the interpretation of participants' emotions, perceptions, and beliefs to shed light on the fundamental essence of the phenomenon under investigation. An essential aspect of the phenomenological research design is the researcher's obligation to set aside any preconceived assumptions about the experience or phenomenon (Delve & Limpaecher, 2012).

Participants of the Study

The study involved a total of fifteen (15) Junior High School students at Lambayong National High School, Division of Sultan Kudarat, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria based on the study of Ngag (2023) where he considered

experts who served as informants and source of data. By this way, Ngag established the generalizability and reliability of the selection.

The inclusion criteria includes the following:

1. The participants must be a Junior High School students.
2. He/she must be one of the students who struggle in the modular class, with record from the adviser/subject teacher.
3. He/she has lowest grade in Science.

Sampling Technique

The study used a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select the Junior High School students at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat who met the specific inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

Purposive sampling, alternately referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, constitutes a variant of non-probability sampling. Within this approach, researchers exercise their own judgment and discretionary acumen in the selection of individuals from the population to partake in their survey endeavors (Alchemer, 2021).

This method of sampling mandates that researchers possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning their study so as to effectively pinpoint and make contact with eligible participants through online survey platforms like Alchemer. Researchers resort to purposive sampling in order to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey respondents are meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion.

Data Gathering Instrument

In this research, a semi-structured interview was utilized as an investigative tool during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to facilitate a thorough exploration of the lived experiences of students at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat.

Initially, the researcher diligently sought formal authorization from the school principal. This step was crucial for obtaining the necessary permissions to conduct the study, highlighting the importance of ethical considerations. Following this, a secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research.

A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, rigorously evaluated, and administered to the targeted participants. The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique to carefully select the elementary school teachers who participated

in the study. Adhering strictly to established health protocols, the researcher conducted face-to-face interviews and facilitated FGDs.

The data collected from the interviews and FGDs were systematically organized, comprehensively analyzed, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This method was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

Data Analysis

In the context of the study centered on exploring the lived experiences of Junior High School students at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat, a content or thematic analysis approach was employed to examine the collected data. This methodology, as described by Flick (2014), involved the systematic categorization of textual components, including statements, phrases, and words, into organized groupings or categories. These categories were either derived from established frameworks or custom-developed to align with the study's specific objectives.

Following data collection, the transcripts were systematically reviewed to identify common themes and patterns emerging from the participants' responses which patterned after the study of Ngag (2023). Through an iterative process of coding and categorization, key themes were identified, reflecting the participants' perceptions, concerns, and insights regarding the agenda.

To execute this analytical process, a series of essential steps were diligently followed:

Initially, all data sources, such as interview transcripts, notes from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and relevant documents, were meticulously organized and prepared for analysis. This phase ensured the systematic arrangement and accessibility of the data.

Subsequently, the researcher deeply engaged with the data by conducting a thorough review of interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process aided in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the content and context embedded within the collected information.

The third step involved initiating a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data. These codes captured essential concepts, ideas, or themes related to communication skills. Following coding, the identified codes were grouped into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step aimed to establish an initial structure for organizing the data.

Next, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes underwent a process of review and refinement. The researcher ensured the consistency and clarity of these themes, making necessary adjustments. Each refined theme was assigned a descriptive

name that succinctly represented the content it encapsulated, facilitating easy identification and interpretation.

Relevant data excerpts, such as quotes or segments extracted from interviews and FGDs, were selected and associated with the respective themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes.

Finally, the thematic analysis extended beyond surface-level identification. Researchers interpreted the meaning and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives. They sought patterns, connections, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of Junior High School students within Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat.

This meticulous and structured process of thematic analysis enabled researchers to systematically explore and comprehend the lived experiences of Junior High School students within the landscape of Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat. Ultimately, this approach yielded valuable insights that could contribute to the enhancement of intervention programs focused on students' lived experiences.

Scope and Limitations

The was conducted at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat during the post-Pandemic time where hybrid class was implemented. It used solely qualitative data gathering technique through in-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD).

It covered the school year 2023-2024, providing a snapshot of the experiences of students during this period. It involved Junior High School students teachers working at Lambayong National High School, DepEd Division of Sultan Kudarat.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The lived experiences of Junior High School students in their modular Science classes at Lambayong National High School

The lived experiences of Junior High School students in their modular Science classes at Lambayong National High School reveal a mixed bag of challenges and adaptations. Many students expressed feelings of isolation due to the lack of face-to-face interaction with teachers and peers, which they found essential for understanding complex scientific concepts.

Despite this, some students appreciated the flexibility that modular learning provided, allowing them to study at their own pace. A recurring theme was the sense of responsibility and self-discipline that students had to develop to manage their time and workload effectively.

The struggles do they encounter that hinder their learning in Science

The students faced several significant struggles that hindered their learning in Science:

Limited Access to Resources: Many students lacked access to adequate learning materials, such as textbooks and scientific equipment, which are crucial for understanding and experimenting with scientific concepts.

Technical Issues: For those using digital modules, frequent technical problems, such as unstable internet connections and lack of proper devices, were major obstacles.

Lack of Direct Interaction: The absence of immediate feedback and direct instruction from teachers made it difficult for students to grasp difficult topics, leading to frustration and decreased motivation.

Distractions at Home: Many students reported that studying at home introduced numerous distractions, making it hard to focus on their studies.

The coping strategies students employ to manage these struggles in their modular Science classes

Students employed various coping strategies to manage these struggles in their modular Science classes:

Time Management and Scheduling: Students created structured study schedules to ensure they allocated sufficient time to each subject, helping them stay organized and on track.

Seeking Help from Family and Peer: Many students turned to family members and peers for assistance with difficult topics, creating informal study groups to support each other.

Utilizing Online Resources: Those with internet access supplemented their learning with online resources such as educational videos, tutorials, and science websites to better understand the material.

Developing Self-discipline: Students worked on improving their self-discipline to minimize distractions and maintain focus during their study sessions.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of the study, the following were concluded:

The lived experiences of Junior High School students in modular Science classes at Lambayong National High School are characterized by a mix of adaptability

and challenges. Students generally appreciate the flexibility of modular learning, which allows them to study at their own pace.

Students encounter several struggles that hinder their learning in Science, including difficulties in understanding complex scientific concepts without the benefit of hands-on experiments and real-time teacher explanations. Additionally, many students face challenges related to inadequate access to learning materials and resources, such as textbooks, internet connectivity, and digital devices.

To manage these struggles, students employ various coping strategies, such as forming informal study groups with peers to discuss and clarify difficult concepts. They also make use of available online resources, such as educational videos and websites, to supplement their learning. Additionally, some students actively seek support from family members or community tutors.

Recommendations

Based on the results, and conclusions, the following were recommended:

1. Department of Education (DepEd) may develop and implement comprehensive training programs for teachers.
2. Curriculum Developers may integrate more interactive and multimedia content into the Science modules, including virtual labs, simulations, and video tutorials, to facilitate a better understanding of complex scientific concepts.
3. Science Teachers may foster the creation of virtual study groups and regular online consultation hours where students can discuss their challenges and seek real-time assistance with their studies.
4. Future Researchers may conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impacts of modular learning on student performance and engagement in Science, and identify best practices for improving modular education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered strictly to ethical compliance guidelines to ensure the integrity and ethical standards of the research process. Formal authorization was obtained from the school principal and the District Supervisor to conduct the study, emphasizing respect for institutional protocols and permissions. Informed consent was secured from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits.

Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were rigorously maintained throughout the research process, with data being securely stored and only accessible to the research team. The study was conducted with sensitivity to the well-

being of the participants, ensuring that no harm came to them as a result of their involvement in the research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her deepest gratitude to her parents, Mr. and Mrs. Jose A. Samaniego, Pang, and Mang, for their unwavering moral support and prayers. Her sisters, Te Beth and Elizabeth S. Espadero, Ph.D., provided invaluable assistance in her career goals, while Ateng Baby, Lucila Villanueva, offered endless advice and prayers.

Special thanks go to her niece, Mary Ann S. Dimamay, MAED, for being her steadfast support system. Her son, John Albert S. Palcullo, has been her inspiration and the driving force behind all her hard work and perseverance.

Finally, she extends her heartfelt appreciation to her school head, Sultan Haron M. Kabugatan of Lambayong National High School, for his understanding and support as her school head.

REFERENCES

- Adedoyin, O. B., & Soykan, E. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic and online learning: the challenges and opportunities. **Interactive Learning Environments**, 1-13.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1813180>
- Alchemer, H. (2021). Purposive Sampling.
<https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/purposive-sampling/>
- Ali, W. (2020). Online and remote learning in higher education institutes: A necessity in light of COVID-19 pandemic. **Higher Education Studies**, 10(3), 16-25.
<https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v10n3p16>
- Delve, J. & Limpaecher, T. (2012). Phenomenological research.
<https://study.com/learn/lesson/phenomenological-research-model-examples-design.html#:~:text=Phenomenological%20research%20involves%20tryin%20to,uses%20interviews%20and%20observation%20notes>
- Department of Education (DepEd). (2020). Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency. DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2020. Retrieved from
https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/DO_s2020_012.pdf
- Flick, J. (2014). Thematic Analysis. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/thematic-analysis/>
- Lapada, A. A., Miguel, F. F., Robledo, D. A. R., & Alam, Z. F. (2020). Teachers' COVID-19 awareness, distance learning education experiences and perceptions towards institutional readiness and challenges. **International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research**, 19(6), 127-144.
<https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.6.8>

Ngag, J.B. (2023). Efficacy of Téduray Literature Module in Teaching English. *CEMJP*, 31(1), 404–409.

<https://doi.org/10.57030/23364890.cemj.31.1.43>

Ngag, J.B. (2023). Unveiling The Literary Appreciation of Teduray Students: A Case Study Analysis of Their Works. *Boletin De Literatura Oral - Tradition Oral Literature*, 10(1), 30-3.

<http://boletindeliteratuoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/5>
